

QUIZ**LAST NAME: RIZK****FIRST NAME: Rana****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following options is considered as a correct in-text citation according to the Chicago Manual of Style?

(Gibaldi 2003, 80)¹.

(*Gibaldi 2003, 80*).

(Gibaldi 2003, 80).

(Gibaldi 2003, 80).

2. As per the Chicago Manual of Style, what would be the recommended format of a paper?

Page dimensions 6.5 by 11 inches, Arial Font 10 inch with indents of 1 inch.

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1* (2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 53.

- Page dimensions 8.5 by 10 inches, Arial Font 10 inch with indents of 1 inch.
- Page dimensions 6.5 by 11 inches, Times New Roman Font 12 inch with indents of 1.5 inch.
- Page dimensions 8.5 by 11 inches, Times New Roman Font 12 inch with indents of 1.5 inch².**

3. **Of the following options, what is the correct bibliography format?**

- Bourdieu, Pierre. "The Market of Symbolic Goods." *In The Field of Cultural Production: Essays in Art and Literature*, ed. Randal Johnson, 112-141. New York: Columbia University Press, 1993³.**
- Bourdieu, Pierre. "The Market of Symbolic Goods." *In The Field of Cultural Production: Essays in Art and Literature*, ed. Randal Johnson, 112-141. New York: Columbia University Press, 1993.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. "The Market of Symbolic Goods." *In The Field of Cultural Production: Essays in Art and Literature*, ed. Randal Johnson, 112-141. New York: Columbia University Press, 1993.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. "*The Market of Symbolic Goods.*" *In The Field of Cultural Production: Essays in Art and Literature*, ed. Randal Johnson, 112-141. New York: Columbia University Press, 1993.

4. **If you were to describe intensively a certain phenomenon in a certain place and time using a qualitative research, what would be a suitable research tradition?**

- Ethnography.
- Phenomenology.

² EUCLID, 49.

³ EUCLID, 55.

- Case Study⁴.**
- Grounded Theory.
5. **There is three type of questions that can be subject of a research: the conceptual type, the practical and the applied type of questions. Which of these types aims to fix a problem or improve a certain situation.**
- Conceptual type of questions.
- Practical type of questions⁵.**
- Applied type of questions.
- All of the above.
6. **Which of these statements describe best the research purpose in a qualitative research study?**
- Seek variation in findings, delves into the “essence” of the topic⁶.**
- Seek Consensus, examine topic to quantify results, investigate relationships and cause-effect phenomena.
- Reach a valid conclusion of a descriptive subject to be understood.
- Answer a strict question with the use of a scientific approach.

⁴ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 1 edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Inc., 2008), 37.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 53

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 16.

7. **Before embarking in a full dissertation, a research student is required to submit a proposal that mainly serve for:**

- Narrowly defining and clearly writing a problem statement.
- Describing how the problem will be addressed.
- Review of the literature and the relevant research to determine what is known about the topic.
- All options are valid⁷.**

8. **Cross the wrong information stated about the European Union.**

- The European Union was established under the treaty of Lisbon⁸.**
- Treaties of accession to the European Union serve setting out principles and regulating ratification.
- Acts of accession of the European Union are acts that contain the technical details of transitional arrangements and secondary legislation *-droit dérivé-* requiring amendment.
- The Twenty-seven (Twenty-five, Fifteen, Twelve, Ten, Nine, Six). These expressions are sometimes used to refer to different memberships of the European Union at different periods.

9. **Which of the following information are valid when writing numbers in dissertations and in the European Commission papers?**

- In deciding whether to write numbers in words or figures, the first consideration should be consistency within a passage.
- Write low numbers (up to nine inclusive) in words.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 18.

⁸ European Commission. 2020. *English Style Guide. A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 58.

- Write large numbers (10 and above) in figures.
- All answers are valid⁹.**

10. **What is not considered a plagiarism act:**

- Reformulating found information into a way that converge with the writer's argument without citations¹⁰.**
- Using another writer's ideas without proper citation.
- Borrowing all or part of another student's paper or having somebody else write your paper or parts of your paper.
- Falsifying data.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

⁹ European Commission, 22.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 50.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.